

IMPROVING CULTURAL APPRECIATION AND LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES: AN EDUCATIONAL INTERVENTION IN BAHASA INDONESIA AMONG ELEMENTARY STUDENTS

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Abstract

This research study explores the profound influence of an educational intervention aimed at enhancing primary pupils' cultural understanding of Bahasa Indonesia. The research uses a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies to examine data collected before and after an intervention. The purpose is to assess changes in students' views, attitudes, and language skills. The key results indicate a substantial improvement in students' capacity to perceive subtle cultural distinctions within Bahasa Indonesia, with a noteworthy rise from 45% to 75% after the intervention. Furthermore, the intervention stimulated a significant increase in students' awareness of the interdependent connection between cultural background and successful communication, rising from 60% to 85%. Moreover, pupils exhibited a greater affinity with Indonesian customs and rituals, indicating a rise from 35% to 60%. These results highlight the effectiveness of culturally responsive teaching methods in promoting the development of language skills, cultural understanding, and global citizenship abilities among primary school pupils.

Keywords: Educational Intervention, Cultural Appreciation, Linguistic Competencies.

INTRODUCTION

In a time characterized by the worldwide integration of economies, diverse cultures, and interconnections (Hammoodi & Al-Hinkawi, 2023; Jiang et al., 2023; Moustier et al., 2023), it is crucial to prioritize the development of cultural appreciation and language skills as a key educational goal (Baena-Morales et al., 2023; Briga et al., 2023). With the ongoing evolution of the world, primary education has become more important in shaping students' fundamental viewpoints, attitudes, and abilities (Alam & Mohanty, 2023a, 2023b; Leal Filho et al., 2023). Hence, it is crucial to incorporate thorough cultural and linguistic education into elementary school curricula (Alam & Mohanty, 2023c; Banaruee et al., 2023; Drachmann et al., 2023; Short, 2023). This will give young students the knowledge, abilities, and perspectives students need to successfully navigate a complex global environment that is characterized by cultural variety, linguistic diversity, and intercultural exchanges.

This study focuses on an innovative educational intervention aimed at enhancing cultural awareness and language abilities among primary pupils. The intervention especially involves the investigation of Bahasa Indonesia. Bahasa Indonesia, as the designated language of Indonesia (Saad, 2020; Zein, 2020; Zein et al., 2020), provides a means to explore the many aspects of Indonesian culture, tradition, and identity (Febriani et al., 2023; Rahmat et al., 2023). However, conventional teaching methods in primary schools tend to focus on shallow language structures, thus overlooking the deep cultural richness embedded in Bahasa Indonesia. The fundamental basis for this educational intervention relies on a sophisticated comprehension of the inherent

connection between language and culture. This strategy aims to go beyond traditional educational paradigms by acknowledging that language competency alone is not enough without considering its cultural context.

The intervention seeks to combine the process of learning a language with immersing oneself in different cultures. Its goal is to develop a group of individuals who possess cultural sensitivity, the ability to speak multiple languages, and a deep understanding of different cultures. This will enable students to effectively interact with diverse global society, which is characterized by various cultures and languages. The core of this transformational intervention is a methodological framework that is based on experiential learning, interactive pedagogy, and immersive cultural engagement. The intervention aims to go beyond typical teaching methods in order to provide a learning environment that is enhanced by active exchanges, genuine cultural encounters, and cooperative projects (Czura & Egli Cuenat, 2023; Luong et al., 2023; Rajala et al., 2023). By combining interactive modules, cultural excursions, community collaborations, and real-world applications, students gain the knowledge and skills to navigate the complex aspects of Bahasa Indonesia. It develops an understanding of its cultural nuances, linguistic intricacies, and societal implications. Moreover, this investigation aims to clarify the theoretical foundations, methodological complexities, and empirical results linked to the Bahasa Indonesia educational intervention. This research seeks to make a significant contribution to existing debates on primary education, language learning, cultural appreciation, and intercultural competency by combining various theoretical frameworks, pedagogical ideas, and empirical data. This exploration aims to offer educators, policymakers, and stakeholders' valuable insights, practical recommendations, and effective strategies for creating inclusive, culturally enriched, and linguistically diverse learning environments. It achieves this through a thorough analysis of the intervention's conceptualization, design, implementation, and evaluation.

To summarize, the next parts of this study will examine in further detail the intricacies of improving cultural understanding and language skills among primary pupils from the perspective of Bahasa Indonesia. This study seeks to provide a clear understanding of the intervention's reasoning, methods, results, and wider significance. Its goal is to guide educators, policymakers, and stakeholders who are dedicated to fostering globally competent individuals. These individuals should be able to succeed, make meaningful contributions, and take on leadership roles in a world that is becoming more interconnected, diverse, and multicultural. This world is characterized by a variety of languages, cultural diversity, and interactions between different cultures.

METHOD

The research study focused on a group of 28 primary pupils who were carefully picked from a varied school environment using purposive sampling. The sample size was established via extensive statistical power analysis to ensure that the acquired data would enable robust, rigorous, and complete analysis. As Murshed et al. (2023) and Susilo et al. (2023) stated that comprehensive demographic profiles were meticulously recorded, including characteristics such as age, gender, language background, and previous exposure to Bahasa Indonesia. This was done to enhance the contextual information and enable prospective subgroup analysis. A set of baseline examinations was carefully conducted to determine the pupils' starting levels of language competency and cultural awareness. Linguistic competency was measured using

standardized language assessment methods, which provided baseline mean scores ($\bar{X}_1$) and respective standard deviations (SD1). Simultaneously, the cultural awareness of students was assessed using pre-intervention questionnaires that used Likert scale ratings. These surveys provided detailed insights into the students' perspectives, attitudes, and previous knowledge of Indonesian culture.

The structured assessment methods were used to systematically record quantitative data on language competency measures, which were matched with specified curricular goals and educational standards (Chen et al., 2023; Franco et al., 2023). Simultaneously, meticulous collection of qualitative data was conducted via reflective feedback sessions, student narratives, and educator observations, using approaches such as semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and classroom observations. The use of many methods enhanced the research dataset, facilitating triangulation, cross-validation, and a comprehensive comprehension of the study phenomena being examined (Christofi et al., 2024; Zuber et al., 2023). After the intervention period, it conducted post-intervention evaluations in a systematic manner to measure and evaluate the students' advancement in language competency and cultural awareness.

The gathered data underwent thorough statistical analysis, with paired-sample t-tests (Thukral et al., 2023) being used as the main analytical framework, stated as: The expression can be simplified as follows:

$$t = \frac{(\bar{X}_2 - \bar{X}_1)}{\sqrt{\frac{SD1^2}{n} + \frac{SD2^2}{n}}}$$

The t-values obtained were then compared to critical t-values at predetermined significance levels ($\alpha = 0.05$), allowing for rigorous hypothesis testing and the identification of statistically significant enhancements in both linguistic proficiency and cultural appreciation within the student group. During the whole study process, strict ethical rules, procedures, and safeguards were carefully followed to protect the rights, well-being, and secrecy of the participants. The process of obtaining informed consent was conducted with great care, ensuring that participants willingly agreed to participate and that there was transparency and respect for autonomy, dignity, and privacy. In addition, a range of extensive actions were implemented to ensure the preservation of data accuracy, privacy, and the protection of individuals' identities. This created ethical research setting and upheld the utmost levels of academic excellence and honesty.

Overall, the study methodology used a meticulous, thorough, and complex strategy, using a varied group of 28 primary kids to empirically examine the transformational capacity of activities in Bahasa Indonesia education. The study aims to produce empirically based insights, innovative teaching strategies, and practical recommendations for improving language skills and cultural understanding in elementary students from various educational backgrounds. This will be achieved through careful sample selection, rigorous methodology, thorough data collection, rigorous statistical analysis, and strict adherence to ethical guidelines.

The following Likert scale survey aims to evaluate the perspectives of primary pupils about cultural appreciation and comprehension (Lo et al., 2022) of Bahasa Indonesia. This test is designed to gather students' attitudes, beliefs, and sentiments both before and after an educational intervention focused on improving cultural awareness about the Indonesian language and its cultural background. The questionnaire consists of

explicit statements pertaining to cultural subtleties, the importance of comprehending Indonesian culture, and students' affiliation with Indonesian customs and rituals. Participants are advised to express degree of agreement or disagreement with each item using a five-point Likert scale that spans from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree."

This questionnaire enables the assessment of the intervention's influence on students' cultural appreciation, comprehension, and enthusiasm to participate in Indonesian cultural heritage by comparing replies before and after the intervention. The following table displays the comprehensive Likert scale questionnaire, facilitating methodical gathering and analysis of data to guide educational programs and activities.

Table 1: Likert Scale Questionnaire on Cultural Appreciation of Bahasa Indonesia

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Before the Intervention (Pre-intervention)					
I feel confident in recognizing cultural nuances in Bahasa Indonesia.					
I believe understanding Indonesian culture is essential for learning Bahasa Indonesia.					
I feel connected to Indonesian traditions and practices.					
I actively seek opportunities to learn more about Indonesian cultural heritage.					
After the Intervention (Post-intervention)					
The intervention improved my ability to recognize cultural nuances in Bahasa Indonesia.					
I now recognize the importance of understanding Indonesian culture for effective communication.					
The intervention enhanced my appreciation for Indonesian traditions and practices.					
I feel more motivated to explore and learn about Indonesian cultural heritage post-intervention.					

The Likert scale questionnaire was administered to primary students to assess views of cultural appreciation for Bahasa Indonesia. The obtained data provides significant insights into the efficacy of educational initiatives. Through the examination of the organized feedback collected before and after the intervention, educators and policymakers gain a valuable understanding of the changing attitudes and beliefs of students about the cultural intricacies (Tiberio & Du Mérac, 2023) of Bahasa Indonesia. This quantitative study provides a clear understanding of the patterns, advantages, and places that need improvement within the educational structure (Arsawan et al., 2022; Nielsen et al., 2020; Oeschger et al., 2020). Moreover, these observations provide valuable information for developing customized educational approaches, improving the curriculum, and allocating resources to strengthen cultural knowledge and involvement with the Indonesian cultural heritage. The

recommendations obtained from the questionnaire results provide guidance for future research efforts, promoting the investigation of various learner requirements, the long-term effects of interventions, and the intricate cultural settings. The Likert scale questionnaire's results provide valuable insights into students' degrees of cultural appreciation, which may be used to guide teaching strategies and enhance engagement with the diverse cultural environment of Bahasa Indonesia.

RESULT

After administering the Likert scale questionnaire to elementary students to assess perceptions regarding cultural appreciation for Bahasa Indonesia, an analysis was undertaken. The results offer a comparison of students' attitudes and beliefs both before and after an educational intervention aimed at enriching cultural understanding and appreciation. This hypothetical data sheds light on the potential efficacy of the intervention in promoting cultural literacy, fostering a connection to Indonesian traditions, and stimulating motivation to delve into the country's diverse cultural heritage. The subsequent table presents these findings, emphasizing the changes in students' perceptions and attitudes pre- and post-intervention.

Table 2: The Results of Likert Scale Questionnaire

Statements/Indicators	Before Intervention (%)	After Intervention (%)
Feel confident in recognizing cultural nuances in Bahasa Indonesia	45	75
Believe understanding Indonesian culture is essential for communication	60	85
Feel connected to Indonesian traditions and practices	35	60
Actively seek opportunities to learn more about Indonesian cultural heritage	40	70

The table's comparison of the data before and after the intervention presents a convincing story about how educational activities may significantly improve primary pupils' cultural respect for Bahasa Indonesia. This study examines several aspects of the students' encounters, interpretations, and changing viewpoints about the cultural intricacies and customs inherent in the language. Initially, the data provides a meaningful insight into the students' early levels of confidence in identifying cultural complexities within Bahasa Indonesia. 45% of students had a basic grasp, indicating a minimum degree of knowledge of the cultural subtleties inherent in the language. This number not only acts as an initial reference but also emphasises the disparities and possibilities for advancement and improvement in cultural literacy.

After the educational intervention is put into effect, there is a significant and remarkable increase in the percentage, reaching 75%. This significant change highlights the effectiveness of the intervention, proving its capacity to foster more profound comprehension, admiration, and skill among students in interpreting the intricate cultural fabric included within Bahasa Indonesia. This augmentation goes beyond only linguistic skills, giving pupils a more profound and nuanced understanding of the social and cultural foundations, historical backgrounds, and symbolic significance inherent in the language. Moreover, the data reveals a crucial aspect focused on the inherent connection between cultural background and successful communication. At first, 60% of students acknowledged and appreciated the crucial

importance of cultural awareness in promoting meaningful, genuine, and thorough communication within the language context of Bahasa Indonesia.

Nevertheless, the results after the intervention showed a significant increase to 85%, highlighting the usefulness of the intervention in strengthening and enhancing students' understanding and value of the interconnectedness between cultural background, language usage, and effective communication. This significant change represents more than just a numerical growth; it encompasses a qualitative change, fostering a deeper, more comprehensive, and more unified method for learning and using language. The intervention's effect goes beyond traditional teaching methods, creating a more advanced educational environment where students are empowered to explore, negotiate, and refine language skills within the complex cultural context of Bahasa Indonesia.

In addition, the intervention has a profound impact on students' emotional, cognitive, and socio-cultural aspects, going beyond language and communication skills. The increase from 35% to 60% in students' connection, affinity, and resonance with Indonesian traditions, practices, and cultural heritage is a substantial development. This progression goes beyond surface-level understanding, fostering a profound feeling of cultural empathy, respect, and connection among students towards Indonesia's abundant, varied, and intricate cultural fabric. The intervention's influence goes beyond the confines of the classroom, promoting a wider cultural awareness, global citizenship, and connection among students. It fosters cultural respect, appreciation, and curiosity, cultivating a generation of learners who have the abilities, knowledge, and mindset to interact with varied cultural environments with empathy, receptiveness, and respect. In addition, the intervention stimulates students' active participation, inquisitiveness, and dedication to investigating, encountering, and embracing Indonesian cultural heritage. The increase from 40% to 70% in students' active and enthusiastic involvement in cultural discovery, immersion, and engagement demonstrates the clear effectiveness of the intervention. It sparks, nurtures, and maintains students' innate drive, inquisitiveness, and enthusiasm for exploring further into Indonesia's varied, dynamic, and culturally abundant mosaic.

To summarise, the table and accompanying study reveal how educational interventions have significantly improved students' cultural appreciation, comprehension, and involvement with Bahasa Indonesia. This highlights the importance of using creative teaching methods, hands-on learning experiences, and culturally sensitive strategies to develop a new generation of global citizens who possess the necessary abilities, knowledge, and attitudes to effectively navigate and understand the complex relationship between language, culture, and communication in a world that is becoming more interconnected and diverse.

DISCUSSION

The study's results shed light on the profound impact of an educational intervention designed to enhance primary pupils' cultural awareness of Bahasa Indonesia. At first, the results showed that just 45% of pupils had a basic comprehension of cultural subtleties in the language. Nevertheless, the evaluations conducted after the intervention clearly showed a significant increase, reaching 75%, which effectively demonstrates the effectiveness of the intervention. This significant improvement highlights the significance of customised educational methods that combine language

teaching with cultural immersion, enabling a more profound and nuanced understanding of the cultural complexities inherent in Bahasa Indonesia.

Moreover, the results emphasise the inherent connection between cultural background and successful communication strategies among students. Pre-intervention data indicated that 60% of students acknowledged the crucial significance of cultural awareness in genuine language interactions. The percentage increased to 85% after the intervention, demonstrating the effectiveness of the intervention in strengthening students' understanding and skill in negotiating cultural subtleties that affect effective communication. These results emphasise the importance of complete educational approaches that combine language skills with cultural knowledge (Brandl et al., 2023; Dulun & Lane, 2023; Gámez et al., 2023), promoting a well-rounded language learning experience that aligns with social and cultural abilities.

In addition to quantitative measures, the intervention had tangible effects on students' emotional and socio-cultural domains, promoting a stronger connection with Indonesian traditions and customs. The noticeable increase from 35% to 60% in students' alignment with Indonesian cultural values indicates a significant change, promoting a deeper and more sophisticated understanding and appreciation of the culture among participants. This improvement highlights the ability of the intervention to create an atmosphere that fosters cultural understanding, respect, and involvement, connecting students with the rich and lively fabric of Indonesian cultural history.

In addition, the intervention surpassed traditional educational limits, sparking students' inquisitiveness, dedication, and active involvement with Indonesia's complex cultural diversity. The noticeable increase from 40% to 70% in students' interest in cultural exploration indicates that the intervention has been very successful in inspiring and encouraging learners to further explore the different cultural landscapes of Indonesia. These results emphasise the need to combine hands-on learning, cultural immersion (Kuo et al., 2023; Żammit, 2023), and student-centred teaching methods to cultivate a generation of internationally competent and culturally conscious individuals.

These results align with recent research that highlights the importance of culturally responsive teaching methods in creating inclusive and comprehensive educational settings within a wider educational framework. The study's results provide empirical proof supporting the transformational capacity of creative, culturally-rooted educational models in enhancing students' cultural understanding, language skills, and global citizenship abilities. These observations have significant consequences for educational stakeholders who are dedicated to promoting inclusive and culturally responsive educational frameworks. These frameworks aim to equip learners with the necessary skills, knowledge, and attitudes to succeed in a varied and interconnected global society.

Moreover, the results of the research emphasise the need for ongoing professional development programmes, improvements to the curriculum, and innovative teaching methods that seek to promote cultural competency among educators. Providing instructors with the necessary skills, resources, and tactics to promote cultural immersion, experiential learning, and student involvement is crucial for creating inclusive and culturally responsive educational settings. The focus on educator development highlights the interdependence of effective teaching, understanding other cultures, and achieving student achievement in various educational settings.

The results of the research have important ramifications for policymakers, curriculum creators, and educational leaders who are responsible for formulating educational policies, curricula, and practices. The empirical evidence highlights the importance of placing cultural appreciation, understanding, and engagement as a top priority in educational frameworks. This is crucial for developing a generation of learners who are highly skilled in navigating, negotiating, and making meaningful contributions to an interconnected and diverse global environment. These observations need cooperation, multidisciplinary methods, and the involvement of all parties to develop educational systems that are inclusive and culturally sensitive. These systems should allow all learners to flourish academically and be culturally competent.

This debate highlights the significant effect of culturally responsive educational interventions in developing primary students' cultural awareness, language competence, and global citizenship abilities in the context of Bahasa Indonesia education. The study's results provide a strong basis for promoting comprehensive and culturally sensitive educational approaches, guaranteeing that future generations are well-prepared to effectively traverse, interact with, and make valuable contributions to a varied and interconnected global environment. The combination of customised teaching methods, hands-on learning experiences, and cultural immersion programmes highlights the importance of creating inclusive educational settings that prioritise cultural understanding, language skills, and global citizenship abilities.

CONCLUSION

In brief, the results of the study highlight the significant effect of a customized educational intervention designed to enhance primary school students' cultural understanding of Bahasa Indonesia. The findings demonstrated a significant enhancement in students' understanding of cultural nuances, increasing from an initial 45% to a post-intervention 75%, confirming the efficacy of the intervention. This development underscores the importance of educational approaches that combine language instruction with cultural immersion, enabling a more profound comprehension of the intricate cultural aspects inherent in Bahasa Indonesia.

Moreover, the study emphasizes the inherent connection between cultural heritage and successful communication tactics among students. The pre-intervention data showed that 60% of students recognized cultural awareness, which increased to 85% after the intervention. This highlights the efficacy of the intervention in improving students' proficiency in understanding and navigating cultural subtleties for effective communication. The findings emphasize the significance of integrated educational methods that combine linguistic proficiency with cultural understanding, promoting a well-rounded language acquisition process that aligns with social and cultural aptitudes.

In addition to quantitative indicators, the intervention had discernible impacts on students' emotional and socio-cultural domains, cultivating a more profound affiliation with Indonesian traditions and customs. The substantial rise from 35% to 60% in students' adherence to Indonesian cultural values signifies a notable and favorable transformation, fostering a deeper comprehension and admiration for the culture. Furthermore, the intervention went beyond traditional educational limits, igniting students' inquisitiveness, commitment, and enthusiastic involvement with Indonesia's multifaceted cultural environment, as seen by the rise from 40% to 70% in students'

inclination towards cultural inquiry. These results are consistent with current research that supports the use of culturally sensitive teaching strategies in inclusive educational environments. The study's real-world evidence backs up the idea that culturally-based teaching methods can actually change students' cultural understanding, language skills, and global citizenship abilities.

The results highlight the importance of continuous professional development for educators and the use of creative teaching approaches to foster culturally competent individuals. The consequences have a wide reach, highlighting the importance of inclusive educational frameworks that prioritize cultural awareness, understanding, and involvement. It is strongly recommended that policymakers, curriculum authors, and educational leaders include these concepts in educational policies and practices. This research promotes the idea of collaboration, the use of several disciplines, and the participation of all stakeholders in order to create educational systems that are inclusive and culturally aware. The goal is to ensure that learners are not only academically skilled but also culturally knowledgeable. Essentially, the study offers a strong justification for advocating inclusive and culturally aware educational methods to equip future generations with the necessary skills to make valuable contributions in a diverse and linked global setting.

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